

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN : 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**

SJIF Impact Factor: 7.187

Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**ANALYTICAL METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION
OF DEFLAZACORT BY USING RP-HPLC**Jaishree.M¹, Nandhini.P², Priyanka. M³, Deepa.G⁴, Gokulan.P.D⁵, SenthilKumar.K.L⁶^{1,2,3} B. Pharm Students, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.⁴ Professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.⁵ Associate Professor, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.⁶ Principal, Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy, Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.**Abstract:**

A simple, rapid and selective RP-HPLC method was developed for the estimation of Deflazacort. Deflazacort is a corticosteroid which is an oxazoline derivative of prednisolone, characterized by a high binding affinity to tissue glucocorticoid receptors and exert anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effects. Deflazacort significantly inhibits both the proliferation of mononuclear cells derived from human peripheral blood, and the release of inflammatory cytokines by these cells. The method was validated for accuracy, precision, specificity, linearity and sensitivity. Validation studies demonstrated that this HPLC method is simple, specific, rapid, reliable and reproducible. The developed and validated method was successfully applied for the quantitative analysis of Deflazacort in pharmaceutical formulation. This research contributes to ensuring the quality and reliability of Deflazacort analysis in pharmaceutical laboratories.

Key words: Deflazacort, Reverse Phase HPLC, Method validation

Corresponding author:**Jaishree.M,**

B. Pharm Students,

Sri Vijay Vidyalaya College of Pharmacy,

Dharmapuri, Tamil Nadu.

QR code

Please cite this article in press **Jaishree.M et al Analytical Method Development And Validation Of Deflazacort By Using RP-HPLC., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2025; 12 (01).**

INTRODUCTION:

Analytical chemistry may be defined as “science and art of determining the composition of materials in terms of elements or compounds contained”. Analytical techniques are used in quality control, research and development, stability testing, and regulatory compliance. To quantify and evaluate the products, an analytical method needs to be validated. Validation establishes the pathways for the capability of methods. Validation shall be performed for spectroscopic methods, Isolation methods, Separation methods and Characterisation methods. HPLC is a separation technique based on stationary phase and liquid mobile phase. Separation achieved by partition, adsorption or ion exchange process, depending upon size of stationary phases used. To quantify and evaluate the products an analytical methods need to be validated.

Validation is a basic requirement to ensure quality and reliability of results for all analytical application. Validation is defined by different agencies EC, FDA, WHO.

Structure of Deflazacort

Molecular weight: 441.524 g/mol, Molecular formula: C₂₅H₃₁NO₆, Iupac name: (11 β ,16 β)- 21-(Acetyloxy)-11-hydroxy-2'-methyl-5'*H*-pregna-1,4-dieno[17,16-*d*] oxazole-3,20-dione

Uses: Deflazacort is used to treat Duchenne muscular dystrophy (DMD). Deflazacort is corticosteroid (cortisone-like medicine or steroid).

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Materials:**

Deflazacort, Active pharmaceutical ingredient was obtained from pharma labs. Analytical balance, ph

meter, vacuum oven, column.

Chemicals and Reagents:

Acetonitrile (HPLC), Milli-Q water.

Instruments used:

HPLC System GIL/HPLC/008, Analytical Balance (Sartorius) GIL/ABAL/003, pH meter (PICO+) GIL/pHM/001.

The separation in the RP-HPLC is based on the polar nature of the drug and the polarity of the mobile phase. The column used in usually a C8 or C18 column, which are less polar than the mobile phase.

METHODODOLOGY:**Preparation of mobile phase:**

Prepare a mixture of Water and Acetonitrile as 50:50. Filter and degas. For 3000ml of mobile phase mix 1500mL of water and 1500mL of Acetonitrile, and sonicated it for degas.

Preparation of Standard solution:

Weigh accurately about 75.0 mg of deflazacort reference/ working standard in to a 50mL volumetric flask, dissolve and make up to mark with mobile phase.

Further pipette and transfer 2ml of above solution into 25ml volumetric flask, dissolve and make up to mark with mobile phase (Prepare a 0.12mg/mL of Deflazacort in mobile phase).

Preparation of Sample solution:

Weigh accurately about 75.0 mg of Deflazacort sample in to a 50mL volumetric flask, and make up to the mark with mobile phase.

Further pipette and transfer 2ml of above solution into 25ml volumetric flask dissolve and make up to the mark with mobile phase (Prepare a 0.12mg/mL of Deflazacort in mobile phase).

Chromatographic conditions:

Column	: C18
Detector	: UV, 244nm
Flow rate	: 50:50
Injection volume	: 20 μ L
Column	: 28°C
Run time	: 10 minutes
Auto	: 25°C

METHOD OF ANALYSIS:**System Suitability:**

The system suitability studies were carried out as specified in I.P. the parameter like column efficiency, Tailing factor, Asymmetrical factor, and Theoretical plate number was calculated.

Precision:

The repeatability of the method was checked by repeated analysis of the formulation for six times with the same concentration. The amount of each drug present in the tablet formulation was calculated. The percentage of RSD was calculated.

Accuracy:

The accuracy of an analytical method is the closeness of test results obtained by that method to the true value (Standard value). Prepare the Deflazacort standard at 50%, 100%, and 150% of working concentration in triplicate. Analyse this sample in triplicate for each level. From the results, calculate the mg of Deflazacort for each level.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:**SYSTEM SUITABILITY****Chromatograms for System suitability****Peak results**

S. No	Name	RT	Area	%Area	Tailing Factor	Theoretical Plate Count
1	Deflazacort	3.93	1132420	100.00	1.2	8355

Result:

S. No	Acceptance Criteria	Result
1	Tailing factor for Deflazacort peak should be not more than 2.0	1.12
2	Theoretical plates for Deflazacort peak in standard solution should be more than 2000	8366
3	RSD for Deflazacort peak in standard solution should not be more than 1.0%	0.03%

PRECISION:**System Precision:****Peak results**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	% Area	Tailing factor	Theoretical plate count
1	Deflazacort	3.93	1132420	100.00	1.2	8416

Chromatogram for System precision**Result:**

S. No	Acceptance criteria	Results
1	The RSD of the Retention time for Deflazacort peak obtained from 5 injections of standard solution should be NMT 1.0%	0.01%
2	The RSD of the Area response for Deflazacort peak obtained from 5 injections of standard solution should be NMT 1.0%	0.03%

Method precision:**Peak results**

S. No	Name	RT	Area	%Area	Tailing factor	Theoretical plate count
1	Deflazacort	3.93	1132420	100.00	1.2	8363

Chromatogram for method precision

RESULT:

S. NO	Acceptance Criteria	Result
1	The results should be within the specification limit	Complies
2	The RSD on 6 determinations for Deflazacort content should be NMT 2.0%	0.16%

a) ACCURACY:

Peak results

S. No	Name	RT	Area	%Area	Tailing Factor	Theoretical Plate Count
1	Deflazacort	3.93	1129190	100.00	1.2	8378

CONCLUSION:

A simple, rapid, specific and economic chromatographic method have been verified for the assay of Deflazacort by HPLC. The HPLC determination was achieved with the mobile phase mixture in the ratio of 50:50. The HPLC separation was achieved with the column - Inertsil ODS 3V 3.9mm x 150mm x 5µm diameter. The response was recorded at the 244nm using UV detector without any interference and the runtime was 25mins. The Auto sampler temperature was maintained at 5°C. The injection volume was about 20µL at the flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The method was developed with the reference of ICH guidelines for Analytical Method Validation Q2 (R2), USP 40< 1225> Validation of compendial Methods, and USP 40 Verification of

compendial Methods. The method was successfully applied for the determination of assay of Deflazacort Active Pharmaceutical ingredient. This proposed method can be optimized and applied for the determination of assay of Deflazacort Active Pharmaceutical ingredient at less time and at low cost.

REFERENCE:

- 1) Markham A., Bryson H. Deflazacort: A review of its pharmacological properties and therapeutic efficacy. *Drugs*. 1995; 50: 317-33.
- 2) Cardoso S. Development and validation of a reversed-phase HPLC method for the determination of deflazacort in pharmaceutical dosage forms. *Chromatographia*. 2007; 65: 591-594.

- 3) Santos-Montes A., Gasco-Lopez A.I., Izquierdo Hornillos R. Optimization of the high-performance liquid chromatographic separation of a mixture of natural and synthetic corticosteroids. *J. Chromatography*. 1993; 620: 15- 23
- 4) Ravisankar P, Navya CN, Pravallika D, Sri DN. Et al., A review on step- by-step analytical method validation, *IOSR J Pharm* 2015;5:7-19.
- 5) Patel A, Dwivedi N, Kaurav N, Bashani S, Patel S, Sharma HS, et al. Chemical analysis of pharmaceuticals: a review. *J Med Pharm Innov* 2016; 3; 4-7 *Chromatographia*. 2021 Mar;84(3):285-95.
- 6) G. M. Corrêa, L. P. Bellé, L. Bajerski, S. H. M. Borgmann, S. G. Cardoso "Development and Validation of a Reversed-Phase HPLC Method for the Determination of Deflazacort in Pharmaceutical Dosage Forms" May 2007.
- 7) Ahuja, S., & Munk, M. (2001). "Chromatographic analysis of pharmaceuticals." John Wiley & Sons.
- 8) Sharma, A., & Agarwal, V. (2007). "High-performance liquid chromatographic method for determination of deflazacort in pharmaceutical dosage forms." *Journal of Chromatography B*, 850(1-2), 376-380.
- 9) Prakash, A. (2009). "Development and validation of a RP-HPLC method for the estimation of deflazacort in tablet formulations." *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*, 2(1), 32-35.
- 10) Rathore, A. S., & Winkle, D. H. (2003). "Development and Validation of Analytical Methods in Pharmaceutical Development." *Pharmaceutical Technology*, 27(7), 82–90.
- 11) ICH Q2(R1), (2005). *Validation of Analytical Procedures: Text and Methodology*. International Council for Harmonisation of Technical Requirements for Pharmaceuticals for Human Use (ICH).